

Supplementary Material—An Adaptive Interactive Routing-Packing Strategy for 3L-SDVRP

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I. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Notations

Consider a network that includes N customer nodes and a singular depot, designated as both the starting and ending points with indices 0 and $N+1$, respectively. The pairwise distances among all nodes are known in advance. At each node, a unique set of boxes is available, with each box characterized by its weight and three-dimensional attributes—specifically, its length, width, and height. The objective is to optimally assign vehicles for the transportation of all boxes, originating from their respective nodes to the terminal depot, with all vehicles commencing their journeys from this starting point.

The notations used in the mathematical model are as follows.

- $G = (V, E)$: road network, a complete directed graph.
- $V = \{0, 1, \dots, N, N+1\}$: the set of vertices; 0 is the starting point; $N+1$ is the ending point; $1 \sim N$ are nodes/customers.
- $E = \{(i, j) \mid i, j \in V, i \neq j\}$: the set of edges.
- d_{ij} : non-negative travel distance, $d_{ij} \neq d_{ji}$.
- $O = \{K_i \mid i = 1, \dots, M\}, 1 \leq M \leq N$: one delivery order/dataset.
- $K_i = \{1, \dots, m_i\}$: the set of boxes that need to be transported in the node i ; m_i : # boxes in the node i .
- $A_i^t \subset K_i$: the set of boxes that are loaded in vehicle t in the node i .
- l_k, w_k, h_k : the length, width, and height of the box k .
- q_k, v_k : the weight and volume of the box k .
- x_k, y_k, z_k : the coordinate of the center of the box k .
- $L_t, W_t, H_t, t = 1, \dots, n$: the length, width, height of container vehicle t ; n : total # vehicles used to transport boxes.
- $Q_t, t = 1, \dots, n$: the weight capacity of container vehicle t .
- $X_{ij}^t = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{vehicle } t \text{ travels from node } i \text{ to } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, i, j = 0, 1, \dots, N+1; t = 1, \dots, n$
- x_{k1}, y_{k1}, z_{k1} : the smallest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the box k in the vehicle.
- x_{k2}, y_{k2}, z_{k2} : the largest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the box k in the vehicle.
- x_{t1}, y_{t1}, z_{t1} : the smallest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the container of the vehicle t (the origin of the coordinate

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system).

· x_{t2}, y_{t2}, z_{t2} : the largest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the container of the vehicle t .

The following are decision variables:

- The number of vehicles used;
- The route (i.e., nodes sequence) of each required vehicle;
- The packing scheme, including the allocation of boxes to vehicles, the 3D coordinates of each box, and the loading sequence for all boxes within each vehicle.

B. A Mathematical Model

The following mathematical model is constructed based on [1]. There are two objectives relevant to both routing and packing aspects of the problem. The first one:

$$\min f_1 = n \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), n is the number of vehicles used.

The second one:

$$\min f_2 = \sum_{t=1}^n \sum_{i=0}^{N+1} \sum_{j=0}^{N+1} d_{ij} X_{ij}^t \quad (2)$$

The optimization process is guided by two conflicting objective functions: f_1 and f_2 . Objective f_1 focuses on minimizing the total number of vehicles utilized, while objective f_2 aims to reduce the total travel distance (ttt) across all vehicles.

Consistent with current research [1]–[7], we treat the inherently bi-objective 3L-SDVRP as a single-objective optimization problem. In this framework, our primary focus is on minimizing the number of vehicles used, while the secondary objective is to reduce the total travel distance [2].

The constraints are as follows.

$$\sum_{j=1}^N X_{0j}^t = 1, t = 1, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N X_{i(N+1)}^t = 1, t = 1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^N X_{ik}^t = \sum_{j=1}^{N+1} X_{kj}^t, k = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=0; i \neq j}^N X_{ij}^t \leq 1, j = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

$$\delta_1 (x_{k2} - x_{l1}) (x_{l2} - x_{k1}) \leq 0, \quad (7)$$

$$k, l \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n$$

$$\delta_2 (y_{k2} - y_{l1}) (y_{l2} - y_{k1}) \leq 0, \quad (8)$$

$$k, l \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n$$

$$\delta_3 (z_{k2} - z_{l1}) (z_{l2} - z_{k1}) \leq 0, \quad (9)$$

$$k, l \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n$$

$$\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3 \in \{0, 1\}, \delta_1 + \delta_2 + \delta_3 \geq 1 \quad (10)$$

$$\bigcup_{t=1, \dots, n} A_i^t = K_i, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (11)$$

$$\bigcap_{t=1, \dots, n} A_i^t = \emptyset, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{b \in B_k} [\min \{x_{b2} - x_{k1}, x_{k2} - x_{b1}\} \cdot \min \{y_{b2} - y_{k1}, y_{k2} - y_{b1}\}] \geq p \cdot w_k l_k \quad (13)$$

$$k \in A_i^t, t = 1, \dots, n; i = 1, \dots, N;$$

B_k : the set of boxes which are below and in contact with the box k in vehicle t

$$\sum_{k \in A_i^t} q_k \leq Q_t, i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (14)$$

$$x_{k1} \geq x_{t1}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

$$y_{k1} \geq y_{t1}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (16)$$

$$z_{k1} \geq z_{t1}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (17)$$

$$x_{k2} \leq x_{t2}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (18)$$

$$y_{k2} \leq y_{t2}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (19)$$

$$z_{k2} \leq z_{t2}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (20)$$

$$I_k > I_l,$$

if Eq. (22, 23, 25) or Eq. (23, 24, 26) hold simultaneously. (21)

In Eq. (21):

$$k \in A_i^t; l \in A_j^t; i, j = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (21a)$$

$$I_k, I_l : \text{loading order of box } k \text{ and } l \text{ in vehicle } R_t \quad (21b)$$

$$(x_{k2} - x_{l1}) (x_{l2} - x_{k1}) > 0 \quad (22)$$

$$(y_{k2} - y_{l1}) (y_{l2} - y_{k1}) > 0 \quad (23)$$

$$(z_{k2} - z_{l1}) (z_{l2} - z_{k1}) > 0 \quad (24)$$

$$z_{k1} \geq z_{l2} \quad (25)$$

$$x_{k1} \geq x_{l2} \quad (26)$$

In this study, constraints are categorized into two main aspects: vehicle routing and 3D loading.

1) **Vehicle Routing Constraints:** Equations (3)–(5) define valid route formation. Each route initiates at a starting node and terminates at an ending node. The depot often serves as both the starting and ending nodes. Additionally, flow conservation must be maintained, meaning that the number of vehicles entering and exiting a node must be equal. Equation (6) enforces a single-visit requirement, ensuring that each customer is visited by the same vehicle only once.

2) **3D Loading Constraints:**

- **Non-overlapping:** Equations (7)–(10) specify that boxes within the same vehicle must not overlap in any dimension.
- **Non-splitting:** Equations (11)–(12) dictate that each box can be loaded into only one vehicle.
- **Supporting Stability:** Equation (13) requires that the supporting area of each box must be at least a percentage p of its bottom area (with $p = 1.0$ in this study).
- **Weight Capacity:** Equation (14) restricts the total weight of loaded boxes to the vehicle's weight capacity.
- **Size:** Equations (15)–(20) ensure that boxes must be contained within the vehicle's container without exceeding the container walls or doors.
- **Last-In-First-Out (LIFO):** Equations (21)–(26) specify that boxes loaded later must be unloaded first, once a vehicle departs from a node.

II. PACKING HEURISTICS

Various packing heuristics are utilized for box loading. One method is to construct vertical layers, as described in [2], [8]. In this method, a "space" denotes an available cuboidal area for box placement. When a box is put into a space, its back-left-bottom corner matches the same corner of the space. This action consumes the original space and generates new, smaller spaces for future loading. It's evident that the formation of these new spaces after a box insertion significantly impacts the algorithm's efficiency. Let s_{curr} represent the current space under consideration for loading, and S_{avail} represent the set of all available spaces. As noted in [2], [8], two boxes are typically loaded simultaneously. The first box is placed into s_{curr} , creating three new subspaces. A second box is then placed into one of these newly-created subspaces, while the remaining two are added to S_{avail} . Importantly, the second box does not produce additional subspaces. If a suitable pair of boxes cannot be found, a single box that fits within s_{curr} is loaded.

Another prevalent method for box loading relies on Extreme Points (EPs), a notion initially introduced by [9] and subsequently adopted across various studies [5], [10]–[13]. EPs are specific points formed by projecting a loaded box along its axes, serving as indicators for available loading space. Each EP indicates the rear-left-bottom vertex of an available space. In EP-based methodologies, the placement of each box generates new EPs, thereby creating new subspaces for future loading. This cycle continues until all boxes are successfully loaded.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table I presents the experimental results, encompassing a variety of approaches. These include our proposed approach, P1R2, R1P2, as well as the current state-of-the-art solution, SDVRLH2, for 3L-SDVRP.

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TABLE I

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS (30 RUNS). SMALL-SCALE INSTANCES: # NODES < 100; LARGE-SCALE INSTANCES: 100 ≤ # NODES ≤ 200. # v = THE NUMBER OF VEHICLE USED; TTD=TOTAL TRAVEL DISTANCE; T = CPU TIME; # FE = THE NUMBER OF FITNESS EVALUATIONS.

Instances (small)	PIR2 (P)						RIP2 (R)						SDVRLH2 (SD)						Ours					
	Avg		Best		# FE	T	Avg		Best		# FE	T	Avg		Best		# FE	Avg		Best		# FE	T	
	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	avg	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	avg	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	lower bound	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	avg	
B-Y1	37	2322.28	37	2202.00	1654.67	82.34	35.20	2526.17	35	2373.10	1504.90	2193.20	37	2081.6	37	2081.6	481696	35.30	2595.89	35	2363	2311.47	20.23	
B-Y2	16	1300.28	16	1143.70	1607.10	31.49	14	1513.34	14	1379.60	1481.23	1132.13	15.5	1055.29	15	1044.2	481696	14.03	1345.50	14	1194	1765.97	90.60	
B-Y3	37	2275.72	37	2187.80	1783.40	81.17	36	2699.66	36	2542.10	1402.00	2638.44	37	2071	37	2071	481696	34.03	2634.20	34	2462.20	2908.30	18.62	
B-Y4	20.97	1497.83	20	1390.30	1683.30	53.90	18.90	1778.39	18	1642.50	1368.30	1386.52	18	1184.62	18	1149.6	481696	17.43	1607.25	17	1454.30	2173.43	12.59	
B-Y5	54	3344.41	54	3248.20	3468.23	228.52	51.50	3710.42	51	3477.60	2786.90	5939.29	54	2961.2	54	2961.2	1057296	51.60	3896.99	51	3678.30	4641.33	47.77	
B-Y6	26.03	2008.80	26	1819.40	3210.57	75.50	24	2384.38	24	2195.50	2661.77	3121.99	25	1570.72	25	1541.4	1057296	23.97	2034.59	23	1875.50	3341.23	20.75	
B-Y7	56.23	3460.90	56	3332.00	3509.90	301.84	55.93	4247.16	55	3948.80	2631.80	7694.59	57	3215.8	57	3215.8	1057296	52.43	4084.05	52	3883	5785.00	51.78	
B-Y8	29	2092.29	29	1975.60	3463.03	121.56	26.17	2824.69	26	2398.50	2253.70	3356.67	26	1645.03	26	1606.8	1057296	24.93	2133.07	24	1902.50	3767.50	25.10	
Sha1	3	563.51	3	562.60	62.90	2.92	3	594.34	3	582.20	69.77	19.84	3	562.6	3	562.6	1816	3	564.89	3	562.60	73.27	1.17	
Sha2	9.03	2812.59	9	2717.70	153.17	3.22	10.03	3201.22	10	3089.10	180.67	26.72	9	2786.6	9	2786.6	5900	9	2853.17	9	2749.70	162.97	1.15	
Sha3	4	403.24	4	393.00	152.47	3.06	4	414.58	4	391.30	149.40	12.93	4	396.48	4	393	17936	4	405.58	4	390.10	159.77	1.15	
Sha4	4	411.42	4	370.40	184.20	4.02	4	382.89	4	354.20	200.30	43.93	4	350.33	4	349.7	22500	4	377.61	4	345	220.33	1.64	
Sha5	6	1437.29	6	1395.70	194.23	3.93	5	1291.51	5	1234.60	208.03	48.30	6	1451.27	6	1447.6	13140	5	1253.00	5	1200.60	196.03	1.44	
Sha6	8	570.29	8	489.20	273.03	4.92	6.73	565.70	6	460.60	286.37	76.62	8	482.13	8	479.6	39856	7	511.36	7	442.50	275.77	1.81	
Sha7	12	1829.88	12	1720.62	353.10	8.28	9	1580.47	9	1470.43	333.57	154.48	12	1707.48	12	1694.8	45340	11	1735.65	11	1651.63	333.43	1.78	
Sha8	8.1	376.61	8	362.60	323.47	5.80	8	375.10	8	359.80	334.53	95.27	8	357.67	8	352.7	30080	8	362.36	8	346	358.20	1.98	
Sha9	13.27	1084.90	13	1017.90	603.80	11.55	12	1025.66	12	953.30	679.53	549.26	13	944.28	13	928.7	116240	12.97	1050.13	12	971.20	672.23	2.96	
Sha10	14.87	1878.30	14	1762.00	818.83	13.29	13.83	1867.75	13	1735.20	888.60	594.03	14	1605.36	14	1590.1	115440	14	1838.85	14	1749.50	907.47	4.37	
Sha11	27	594.66	27	565.60	1540.67	33.27	25.90	630.40	25	586.00	1697.00	3262.19	26.2	523.21	26	521.5	575640	25.93	604.78	25	561.90	1687.90	9.84	
Sha12	16.27	3302.54	16	3044.00	888.70	13.39	14.60	3364.60	14	3043.90	1075.07	750.87	17	2968.08	17	2942.1	250736	15	3101.30	15	2898.70	1036.60	4.89	
Sha13	29	3733.92	29	3624.33	2149.43	39.00	26	3610.61	26	3430.30	2334.87	4529.10	27.7	3147.93	27	3097.3	907644	27.33	3577.92	27	3398.90	2611.53	14.48	
SD1	5	5471.70	5	5032.29	169.00	4.31	5	6135.12	5	5541.58	172.73	62.94	5	5238.5	5	4941.8	13680	5	6074.25	5	5450.05	218.20	1.55	
SD2	13	12771.11	13	11952.14	575.07	11.81	14	14205.47	14	13068.21	603.20	193.85	14	11929.8	14	11620.2	99096	13	13335.03	13	12000.66	627.20	3.76	
SD3	23	18744.37	23	17666.93	832.03	14.54	23	19907.35	23	18753.64	895.10	206.40	23	16302.1	23	15800.9	154480	23	19350.28	23	17263.02	984.23	6.59	
SD4	14	16020.54	14	14078.15	1025.87	14.46	13	17596.73	13	15868.70	936.60	296.20	14	12826.7	14	12655.5	225400	13	16188.88	13	14549.59	919.57	5.16	
SD5	36	25743.78	36	25713.05	858.43	10.77	2	6503.57	2	5944.45	629.43	56172.80	17	14513.8	17	14513.8	315040	18	15741.52	18	15090.33	1253.77	7.86	
SD6	16	18682.55	16	17090.42	1218.77	202.28	15	19543.27	15	17799.98	1354.07	45115.95	17	15883.7	17	15332.5	272960	14	21217.44	14	18524.40	1594.73	19.56	
SD7	11	14514.24	11	12839.92	1180.23	13.40	10.90	17159.10	10	15255.58	1302.13	462.93	13	12206.6	13	11804.4	342776	10	14960.53	10	12800.52	1366.13	7.30	
SD8	21	21833.92	21	20124.75	1438.17	130.54	20	23382.14	20	21671.83	1478.87	8883.11	23	19709.8	23	19225.8	394140	19	24961.50	19	22985.21	1860.47	14.79	
SD9	18	20116.60	18	18459.02	1789.87	44.24	16.97	21208.31	16	19419.95	1970.27	5574.62	20	16512.9	20	16015	551820	16.27	21285.94	16	18263.40	2200.93	9.67	
SD10	11	16019.75	11	14720.73	2112.17	46.13	10	18609.53	10	15686.17	1642.13	5617.69	18	16432.6	18	15874.5	569236	8.33	16300.24	8	14291.96	1873.97	10.84	
SD11	11	20645.54	11	17393.06	3219.40	153.25	9	21788.35	9	19355.59	2541.57	44943.61	21.1	18871.3	21	18593.2	2197140	9	20152.01	9	17631.18	2704.83	17.93	
Avg	19.1	7120.8	19.0	6574.8	1328.0	55.3	17.0	7082.1	16.7	6437.9	1189.2	6411.1	19.0	6046.8	18.9	5912.4	419812.6	17.1	7129.2	16.9	6404.1	1593.6	11.2	
Total	609.8	227865.7	607.0	210395.1	42497.2	1768.7	542.7	226628.0	535.0	206014.3	38054.4	205156.5	606.5	193496.5	605.0	189195.5	13434004.0	548.6	228135.8	542.0	204931.5	50993.8	359.6	

Instances (large)	PIR2 (P)						RIP2 (R)						SDVRLH2 (SD)						Ours					
	Avg		Best		# FE	T	Avg		Best		# FE	T	Avg		Best		# FE	Avg		Best		# FE	T	
	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	avg	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	avg	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	lower bound	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	avg	
B-Y9	71.47	4552.29	71	4414.60	5618.87	326.41	68.13	5129.77	67	4855.70	4176.20	10646.01	71	4014.9	71	4014.9	2041396	68.40	5142.87	68	4816.50	8157.47	60.48	
B-Y10	35	2686.30	35	2496.30	5568.17	155.47	31.57	3243.72	31	2944.70	4279.90	5534.83	34.7	2133.53	34	2077.3	2041396	31.73	2736.21	31	2556.40	5859.07	46.90	
B-Y11	75	4647.18	75	4535.10	6326.50	585.02	74.17	5953.84	74	5540.00	3550.47	13905.65	76	4386.7	76	4386.6	2041396	69.90	5492.88	69	5163.20	8935.77	80.35	
B-Y12	39	2849.86	39	2746.80	5588.90	260.02	35.03	3830.06	35	3445.00	3965.13	7029.40	34	2173.56	34	2151.3	2041396	32.97	2820.43	32	2590.90	7007.43	55.02	
B-Y13	108.83	6652.01	108	6325.60	11903.40	924.13	103.97	7474.54	103	7112.90	9035.77	35377.39	109	6043.42	109	6022.4	5332096	104.33	7556.39	104	7216.00	15354.77	165.78	
B-Y14	50.67	3879.77	50	3670.20	10230.53	405.80	45.10	4609.82	45	4071.00	9175.93	19368.71	48	2942.14	48	2888.3	5332096	45.40	3816.64	45	3532.20	12453.57	86.33	
B-Y15	111.87	6773.99	111	6570.70	11360.37	1179.49	110.37	8838.59	109	8172.40	6977.27	43874.23	117.6	6477.68	117	6451.1	5332096	104.23	7919.19	103	7448.30	19648.93	214.33	
B-Y16	57.93	3974.64	57	3773.70	11045.57	548.28	52.80	5555.51	52	4981.50	7819.63	18133.88	51.9	3089.77	51	3177.8	5332096	49.77	3998.19	49	3678.80	14121.57	132.15	
B-Y17	144.53	8534.11	144	8294.10	20076.67	2082.02	138.23	9699.21	137	9273.20	15737.37	110410.24	148	8462.34	148	8456.4	11464784	138.67	9789.79	137	9460	25780.17	469.91	
B-Y18	65.33	4886.61	65	4559.10	16068.20	724.38	58.73	5938.78	58	5520.50	1438													